

From Culture to Citizenship: How Green Job Crafting Shapes the Impact of Green Organizational Culture on Environmental Behavior

Muhammad Tufail

Department of Human Resource and Information Management
Institute of Business Studies and Leadership, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan
Email: tufail@awkum.edu.pk

Muhammad Haroon Ur Rashid

Department of Human Resource and Information Management
Institute of Business Studies and Leadership, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan
Email: haroon@awkum.edu.pk

Ismael Afzal

Department of Human Resource and Information Management
Institute of Business Studies and Leadership, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan
Email: ismael@awkum.edu.pk

Abstract

Regardless of the formal job practices used to convert business strategy into employee actions, green behavior plays a crucial role in influencing employee green behavior has received enough attention. This study aims to investigate the relationship between green workplace culture and workers' organizational citizenship behavior for the environment. Further the moderating role of green job crafting in a link between green organizational culture and organizational citizenship behavior for the environment has also been explored. Hotel staff in Pakistan's northern regions was chosen at random to participate in this study. Results revealed the direct relationship between green organizational culture and organizational environmental citizenship behavior. Additionally, the moderating role of green job crafting was also confirmed. The findings of the study contribute hospitality organizations a starting point for their emphasis on environmental citizenship behavior and green organizational culture. To further encourage employees' favorable response to ecologically specialized green workplace cultures and organizations, practitioners must also help them align their values with those of the company.

Keywords: Green organizational culture, green job crafting, organizational environmental citizenship behavior, tourism.

Introduction

Despite being a key driver of economic growth worldwide, tourism also contributes considerably to environmental deterioration (Irfan et al., 2023). Overuse of natural resources, pollution, biodiversity loss, and higher carbon emissions have all been

linked to mass tourism (Deb et al., 2023). Consequently, the necessity of sustainable tourism approaches has emerged as a critical issue for scholars, practitioners, and policymakers alike. Tourism organizations are responding to these issues by implementing more environmentally sustainable practices, focusing on the role that company culture plays in encouraging ecological consciousness (Qu et al., 2022). Furthermore, consumer boycotts, choices, and moral standards are now affecting the corporate environment, which affects their attempts to achieve a competitive edge (Agyabenh-Mensah et al., 2024). Due to a growing consciousness of moral and environmental behavior among residents, employees, and tourists, sustainability has become crucial to hotel management (Ogretmeno glu et al., 2022). Consequently, the hotel sector has been emphasizing environmental preservation through initiatives including recycling, reusing linens, cutting back on waste, conserving electricity and water, and educating customers (Alola et al., 2022). Hotels that care about the environment have more guests, satisfy their needs, and benefit from staff members' dedication to sustainability, which helps them remain above their competitors (Yang et al. 2023). Since it encourages green staff behaviors, hotels must have a green mindset and eco-friendly procedures (Darvishmotevali and Altinay, 2022). Such actions may mitigate a hotel's impact on the environment and encourage guests who are prepared to spend more for eco-friendly lodging (Ogretmeno glu et al., 2022).

Considering the improvements and development of ecological environmental efficiency, employees exhibit and involve in extra organizational behavior such as organizational environmental citizenship behavior (OECB) has been emphasized by research studies (Agyabenh-Mensah et al., 2024; Alola et al., 2022). Hence, for 'environmentally friendly' firms, such voluntary pro-environmental practices as OECB must be ensured to be in place (Gurmani et al. 2021). The hospitality industry places a significant stress on businesses to acknowledge and foster voluntary pro-environmental behaviors by its employees to effectively deal with environmental challenges (Elshaer et al., 2022). OECB is a recent concept and has caught the eyes of researchers scholars (Khan et al., 2021; Zaidi and Azmi, 2024). Elshaer et al., (2022), observed scanty literature on the subject and most times, scholars and researches tend to ignore the importance of employees' OECB in promoting organizational environmental performance. Khan and et al., (2002) also noted that since the causes of OECB is unsatisfactorily studied, it is important to expand our understanding about its antecedents. As for the hotel industry, the mechanisms of OECB have an imbalance (Luu, 2019). These results call for additional research that can help enrich employee green behavior theory and practice, especially in the hotel context.

According to Chen et al. (2020), organizational green culture (OGC) is a matrix of assumptions, values and artifacts that an organizational needs concerning environment friendly operations. It provides useful information to managers and helps to increase staff awareness of environmentally friendly practices and conservation (Chandra et al., 2021). Promote greener principles to the corporate level and embed them as corporate culture is important for efficient environmental management (Song et al., 2020). Eco-friendly strategies, training of green, sustainable service delivery formats, and active leadership commitment towards environmental goals are few instances that how a

green corporate culture may look like in the tourism industry (Srivastava et al., 2024). Such cultural predispositions shape employees' informal practices, which ultimately are central for the success of sustainability initiatives and contribute to creating competitive market advantages and regulatory compliance (Al-Swidi, et al., 2021). When sustainable practices are embedded in daily operations and in a culture of individual and group responsibility for environmental outcomes, a robust green corporate culture can serve as a vehicle for OCBE (Muisyo et al., 2022). Employees who work in institutions that pay significant concern to sustainability are more likely to identify and incorporate prosocial and pro-environmental norms in facilitating their OCBE.

Although the tourist industry is starting to be more embraced to sustainability no abundant evidence in the literature is available on the association between green organizational culture and OCBE (Pham et al., 2019), particularly in developing countries. There is a void regarding how such mechanisms operate in tourism firms where the interrelationship between human activity and environmental impact is more apparent and direct, despite the emphasis given in the literature to the corporate or production sectors (Zientara, & Zamojska, 2018).

Although a green company culture provides the basis for environmental involvement, there can be wide variations in how much an employee really reflects these standards (Al-Swidi et al., 2021). The variability suggests that characteristics at the individual level for example, personal environmental values and concern, green identity, moral attitudes, cognitive competence, organizational identification, and self-efficacy may influence how workers react to organizational culture (Subramanian, & Suresh, 2023). Similarly, green job crafting is a proactive approach through which employees modify their work duties, interpersonal interactions, and attitudes according to environmental objectives (Luu, 2019). By actively pursuing green behavior, subordinates can support an environmentally conscious approach and the organization's overall sustainability (Elshaer et al., 2023; Tuan, 2021). Job redesign may foster an environment where employees are motivated to deliberately perform more than formal job demands (Demerouti et al., 2015). This is because being proactive enhances one's confidence to act in new ways (Hornung & Rousseau, 2007). Additionally, there may be a greater person-environment fit when workers design their work and work environment (Tims & Bakker, 2010). To feel good, stay motivated, and perform effectively at work, proactive employees acquire the resources they need (Tims et al., 2012).

Green job crafting may serve as a moderating factor, enhancing the favorable correlation between green organizational culture and OECEB. Although there is limited direct empirical examination of green job crafting as a moderator, some related studies indicate that green organizational culture's environmental dimensions can facilitate and enhance OECEB (Liu, & Yu, 2023). According to Pham et al., (2018), green organizational culture moderates the effect of green training on OCBE, with a positive influence on OCBE. This suggests that the impact of ecotraining on staff's discretionary pro-environmental behaviour could be strengthened by a positive green cultural setting. For example, the green corporate climate policy of hotels has a significant positive effect on OECEB, which suggests that the organizational support is

vital to cultivate employees' environmental citizenship development (Zientara & Zamojska, 2018). Organization environmental principles are easier to be embedded and put into practice through the engagement of employees in green job crafting. Employees who do not engage in this type of skill, in contrast, may become passive carriers of the general organizational culture, and this would result in a less positive behavioral outcome. Thus, enabling workers to express environmental values in their work roles actively and independently as with green job crafting, in addition to guards' interaction with green organizational culture, may enhance OECB. These results highlight how crucial green corporate culture is to improving OECB and imply that employee-driven activities like green job crafting may strengthen this relationship. Accordingly, the objective of the study is to enhance knowledge on how organizational values and personal autonomy interact to facilitate sustainability related behavior, especially within service intensive sectors as tourism.

Literature Review

GOC and OECB

One such internal resource that is crucial to creating effective environmental initiatives is green organizational culture (Hart, 1995). Green Organizational Culture (GOC) refers to the culture of an organization that encourages employees to work in a manner that protects the environment and fosters an atmosphere that encourages the growth of creative concepts, attitudes, teamwork, behavior, etc. in a way that minimizes the organization's adverse environmental effects (Chen, 2011). The culture of an organization is considered "green" if its personnel act and think beyond the pursuit of profit in order to maximize the positive impact of the business's activities while reducing their detrimental effects on the environment around them (Roscoe et al., 2019). According to Li et al. (2011), GOC-based companies recognize and assess various kinds of issues, propose solutions, and deal with them in line with ecological values.

Green values must be adopted by all employees for environmental management to be implemented successfully in organizations (Yeşilta et al., 2022). Environmental oriented green culture can be developed through ensuring green values (Galpin et al., 2015) and environmental sustainability can also be the result of green culture (Govindarajulu & Daily, 2004). Culture influences employees to exhibit certain behavior (Gürlek and Tuna, 2018). Employees are expected to behave environmentally friendly in an organization whose staff is committed to green cultural principles (Yeşilta et al., 2022). A behavior that supports workplace environmental sustainability initiatives is OECB (Jackson et al., 2012). The organization's identity, culture, and structure impact employee attitudes and behaviors (Lasrado and Zakaria, 2020). Similarly, according to Paillé et al., (2013), that an employee is more inclined to make extra eco-efforts when they believe their company supports them in performing in a pro-environmental approach by giving them the resources they require. When businesses adopt environmentally friendly management practices and supportive environmental policies, employees are more inclined to act in a responsible way at work (Paillé et al., 2014). While employees are aware of the organization's

green policies and experience organizational support for a healthy work environment, an individual's organizational commitment matures, which in turn boosts their eco-behavior (Temminck et al., 2015). Organizations follow such green work policies which have impact on OECB (Zientara, & Zamojska, 2018). Promoting a green culture might inspire staff members to act in an environmentally friendly way (Pham et al., 2018). Therefore, In order to enhance OCBE, a green corporate culture is required. Thus, it is hypothesized that:

H1: Green organizational culture has significant impact on Organizational environmental citizenship behavior.

Green Job Crafting

Job crafting is the term used to describe the changes employees make to their work to make it more aligned with their personal strengths, passions, or values (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). Applying this to the sustainability context, we propose that green job crafting refers to employees' self-initiated activities to change job tasks, job-role boundaries, and interacting relationships for the purpose of their environment-enhancing impacts (Zhang & Parker, 2019). For instance, adapting working practices to cut costs to the environment, working on environmental projects with fellow workers or re-positioning one's work in environmental language. Green job crafting was a job crafting variation related to an individual's environmental identity, as well as personal contribution to the environment, which leads to an enhancement in work meaningfulness and green performance (Niessen et al., 2016).

Employee Job Crafting and Citizenship Behavior

Citizenship behaviors of employees, while not mandated for job performance or specified in job specifications, are crucial for attaining exceptional service quality, efficient organizational functioning, and customer happiness (Liao et al., 2009). Based on the crafting theory, we claim that employees' job crafting activities are predominantly motivated by the need to fulfill their psychological needs and to achieve their work objectives (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). Other stakeholders within a company may benefit from the indirect effects of employees' job crafting. People are encouraged to transform their roles and structures to better suit the setting during this type of "role reinvention" process. Additionally, creating with one's social surroundings facilitates more good connections with people (Vogel et al., 2016). For example, employees may use structural and social resources (e.g., developing their professional capabilities in serving customers, learning new skills to efficiently accomplish time-consuming tasks, and looking to their supervisor for inspiration or asking colleagues for advice) if their jobs require them to handle demanding customers or accept less desirable work duties. Such discretionary behaviors may therefore be affected by active participation in job creating activities with the goal of achieving customer satisfaction and leaders' or coworkers' expectations (Lyons, 2008). Additionally, job designing helps workers meet psychological requirements, regain work engagement, and lessen the sense that they are not a good match for their position (Tims et al., 2012). The advantages of job crafting may prevent fatigue and

disengagement, which keeps individuals motivated to go above and beyond for their boss, colleagues, and clients. In fact, recent empirical research on job crafting showed that employees who participated felt more engaged and that their jobs were more compatible, which in turn encouraged them to do more civic duties (Vogel et al., 2016). Indeed, the benefits of job crafting to the actor have been extensively established in the literature. These benefits include greater levels of job satisfaction, less turnover, improved person-job fit, increased engagement, improved meaning of work, and the development of positive identities (Bakker, Tims, & Derks, 2012; Wrzesniewski et al., 2013). Therefore:

H2: Green Job Crafting has significant impact on Organizational environmental citizenship behavior.

Moderating role of Green Job Crafting

Employees actively seek out resources pertaining to green initiatives by "crafting" their work duties and responsibilities to engage in environmentally responsible practices, as environmental concerns are becoming increasingly relevant in the modern business environment (Garg, & Arora, 2025). The interrelationship between green OC and green JC is a new subject in the field of sustainability behavior studies. On the one hand, the green organizational culture tells us what the rules of the game are and green job crafting is a demonstration of it, but there is also a space of maneuver that individuals have, and they actually do something on their own in addition to what the organization asks in one form or another. Workers participating in green job crafting may be more willing to embrace green culture by turning on the shared green values into action than those who do not participate in it. In contrast, players who do not craft may be less likely to exhibit OCBE even in an organization that has a culture supportive of such activities. There is evidence for job crafting moderating the impact of organizational context on employee outcomes (Susanto et al., 2025; Böhnlein, & Baum, 2020), though limited work has examined this specifically for environmental behavior.

This lack is where we live, and we close it by suggesting that green job crafting may moderate the relationship between green organizational culture and OCBE. That is, the positive relationship between green culture and OCBE will be stronger when employees have greater engagement in green job crafting. This moderating effect suggests that personality traits can be manifested in behaviors promoting the environment, as it is not inherent in one's values but a product of the interplay between organizational values and personal initiative leading to pro-environmental behaviors in the workplace.

Organizations especially in tourism industry where sustainability and stakeholder expectations are high, it is prominence in business strategy. For organizations that are interested in developing an environmentally friendly behavior in their members, studies have revealed two important variables: green organizational culture and Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE). Drawing on the assumption that the green organizational culture serves as the base for eco-values and environmental norms, the translation of these values into real behaviors and practices,

such as OCBE, can be affected by individuals' factors, mainly green job crafting. Therefore:

H3: Green job crafting moderates the relation between green organizational culture and organization environmental citizenship behavior such that the relationship will be stronger for higher green job crafting.

Methodology

Hotels were randomly selected in northern areas of Pakistan. The selection of these hotels was based on their essential role in promoting environmentally friendly behavior, a crucial factor in hotels' reputation (Kang & Bartlett, 2013). The researcher approached the managers and described the purpose of the study, ensured the anonymity of the participants and permission was granted to collect the data from their respective employees. The study's target population comprised individuals in entry-level management positions with a minimum of one year hotel of experience, together with their corresponding supervisors. A list of 2500 employees along with 800 supervisors was obtained from the hotels' management. Among the lists, employees and their respective supervisors were randomly selected; each employee and supervisor was given a unique code to match their responses. To avoid any bias in data collection, the data was obtained in two phases.

The selected hotels were personally visited and the employees were requested to fill the questionnaires. The participants were approached to participate in this study. Employees were given the survey immediately following by their respective supervisors. The participants in this study provided appropriate responses, despite the reduced response rate. Prospective participants were requested to complete the survey voluntarily. In the first phase, 670 participants were participated in the study. This section contained demographic information and responses on the green organizational culture and green job crafting along with names of respective supervisors, so they can be approached in the second phase of data collection. The collected valid questionnaires were 408. At time two, after four weeks apart, responses were recorded from supervisors regarding their immediate subordinates about the green environmental green behavior. 403 matching employee-supervisor pairs were collected which were fit for further analysis. Among these respondents 72.7% of the participants were male, 83.5% of the respondents were having a 16 years formal qualification and 51% were at manager position.

Measures

All the items were on five-points Likert scale ranging where 1 denoted strongly disagree and 5 denoted strongly agree. The scales were adopted from previous studies. GOC was measured by 8 items scale of Subramanian and Suresh (2023), to assess the Green job crafting a scale of Petrou et al., (2012) including 3 items and lastly a 10 items scale of OCBE was utilized developed by Boiral and Paillé (2012).

Control Variable

Consistent with previous studies on green behavior (Saeed et al., 2019; Faraz et al., 2021; Mughal et al., 2024) demographic variables were treated as control variables. It was found that age and gender was significantly correlated with OCBE and was considered as control variables.

Results

Measurement model

Table 1 displays the reliability, composite reliability and composite validity. All the obtained values are above the threshold value of 0.7, indicating the reliability of the constructs (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 1. Construct reliability

Construc	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)
OCBE	0.79	0.79	0.86
GOC	0.78	0.78	0.86
GJC	0.77	0.77	0.85

Table 2 shows the validity of the constructs through average variance extracted (AVE) and Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT). The obtained values show that both the validities (convergent and discriminant) were acceptable, the obtained AVE values were above 0.5 and HTMT values were below 0.90 (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 2. Construct validity

Construct	AVE	HTMT 1	2	3	4
OCBE	0.54	-			
GOC	0.54	0.83	--		
GJB	0.59	0.80	0.85	--	
GOCxGJC		0.35	0.23	0.32	--

Hypotheses Testing

Confirming the reliability and validity, collinearity of the model was measured. Variance inflation factors (VIF), which Kock (2016) suggested address common method bias, was utilized for the assessment. The values have been presented in table 3, denotes that the obtained values are within the acceptable range of < 3.3.

Table 3. Collinearity

	VIF
GOC ---OCBE	2.17
GJC ---OCBE	2.11
GOCxGJC---OCBE	1.09

The values of effect sizes and test of hypotheses have been presented in table 4. The bias-corrected and accelerated (BCa) data from 10,000 bootstrapping subsamples were used to assess the hypotheses' relevance (Sarstedt et al., 2023). The BCa confidence interval of hypotheses did not contain any zero and thus were supported. The effect size of moderated path was subject to interpretation of Kenny (2018).

Table 4 Test of hypotheses and effect sizes

Path	Beta	SD	T-value	Confidence interval	f-square
GOC--OCBE	0.65**	0.04	20.91	0.596-0.698	0.71
GJC--OCBE	0.38	0.06	6.96	0.293-0.472	0.26
GOCxGJC--OCBE	0.13	0.04	5.00	0.083-0.181	0.13

Note(s): **p < 0.001

Discussion

In recent years, importance of developing green organizational culture to respond to increasing environmental issues and to further enhance corporate sustainability performance is stressed by scholars as well as practitioners (Norton et al., 2015). This type of culture not only guides organizational policies but also has a strong impact on employee behavior, most notably in the form of OCBE (Boiral & Paillé, 2012). Emerging empirical evidence also supports the positive relationship between green organizational culture and OCBE (Dumont et al., 2017). The cultures of these organizations also foster the pursuit of environmental friendly behavior as an expected or normative behavior in organizations as well as a source of organizational pride. Such cognition helps to drive employee intrinsic motivation to engage in the environmentally friendly practices that not only are top-down forced or rewarded (Norton et al., 2015). When an organization clearly upholds environmental values, employees are strongly attached to the organization and feel a sense of responsibility to contribute to the sustainability of the organization through OCBE (Kim et al., 2017). When employees believe their organization is truly invested in ecological issues, they respond by developing attitudes and behaviors that are positively associated with being loyal and with undertaking green initiatives, based on the tenets of Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964). Although the evident positive association, it is argued that creating the organizational culture green may not by itself ensure extensive OCBE. Additional constructs such as support from management, individual's values toward the environment, as well as the opportunity to participate can strengthen or attenuate this relationship (Robertson & Barling, 2013; Dumont et al., 2017). However, building a green culture is still a fundamental approach to developing OCBE, since it builds a context whereby sustainability is embedded in organizational life.

Green job crafting is a key driver of pro environmental behavior in the workplace, in particular, OECEB which refers to employees' proactive redesign of their jobs,

relationships, and evaluation of the meaning of work to include environmental sustainability in their role (Zhang & Parker, 2019). The creation of meaning at work in crafting work reflects a grass-roots process to work where employees shape their own work experiences around personal values and ecological interests (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). Preliminary studies imply that green job crafting has direct impact on OCBE. Individuals who engage in green job crafting have stronger perceptions of meaningfulness and purpose at work, which should foster intrinsic motivation for going above and beyond the call of duty as it relates to environmental behaviors (Tims et al., 2013; Zhang & Parker, 2019). Green job crafting is an important facet for translating personal environmental values into organizational behaviours. Strength of pro-environmental values among employees might not always be translated into behavior, unless they feel the freedom and space to adopt sustainability goals in their jobs (Zhang & Parker, 2019). Green job crafting enables anchorages, making connections between individual values and OCBE (Paillé et al., 2016). For instance, Dumont et al. (2017) indicated that green HRM-related practices initiate psychological climates for sustainability, but the translation of these climates into actual green behaviors is indeed significantly boosted by individual level factors such as green job crafting. Similarly, Kim et al. (2017) revealed that employees adjusting their work activities to include sustainability are more prone to make voluntary contributions to the organization in relation to its environmental objectives.

There are increasing evidences that highlights the important influence of green organizational culture in fostering employees' pro-environmental behaviors (Robertson & Barling, 2013; Norton et al., 2015). A climate of such a nature has been consistently associated with higher levels of OCBE (Boiral & Paillé, 2012). Yet, the translation of green culture as perpetual OCBE is not instant and there are individual-level mechanisms that may be facilitating that employees are adopting and indigenizing those organizational codes (Dumont et al., 2017). In this context, green job crafting appears to be an important moderating variable. By proactively making their jobs correspond to environmental values, they may translate cultural signs into actual OCBE more effectively (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001; Tims et al., 2013). So, employees who redesign work flows that eliminate waste or increase energy efficiency make the culture's green vision actionable through tailored action. Additionally, green job crafting might increase the feeling of possession of the work of Green initiative of the environment, thereby strengthening the effect of OCBE (Dumont et al., 2017). When they perceive that they have co-produced their environmental roles, employees are more committed and proactive. This is consistent with Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000), that green job crafting meets the intrinsic needs for autonomy and competence, converting green culture into long-term voluntary actions. In sum, the moderating role of green job crafting emphasizes the need for promoting an environment that allows employees not only to passively implement prescribed environmental activities but to also proactively design their work around ecological targets. Firms that aim to greater profit from a green culture and its influence on OCBE should thus develop encouraging climates for employees'

job crafting, granting employees' autonomy and support to (re)design their roles in a sustainable way.

Practical implication

The findings have important implications on practical persuasion for managers in tourism companies who have the desire to convert their green organizational culture into concrete green outcomes through the OCBE of employees, while developing a green organization is important, managers should be aware that green organizations are not enough to ensure high level of OCBE. Individuals evaluate that they have the freedom and the ability to include environmental values to their particular job. This makes it apparent that the cultivation of green job crafting a proactive behavior of employees in altering their work tasks, interactions, and perceptions in order for them to be compatible with environmental sustainability is critical.

Similarly, training and development programs on job crafting skills may be adopted by managers in tourism institutions (such as in hotels, tour operators and visitor attractions). For instance, training courses may enable employees to spot ways to minimize waste and consumption or to design guest experiences based on environmentally-friendly products, or sustainable innovations in services and operations (Martínez-Martínez et al., 2019). These activities do not only enhance the skill sets of employees, but also communicate that green job crafting is supported and appreciated by the organization. Leaders may also make it explicit that employees are trusted to creatively repurpose their work for these sustainability goals. Leadership practices which empower employees and signal support for environmental innovation shape a psychological climate conducive to the crafting of green jobs (Robertson & Barling, 2013; Dumont et al., 2017). In the tourism industry, desirable consequences are particularly relevant, since an employees' behavior has an immediate influence on service quality and customer perceptions. Tourists place more emphasis on authentic sustainability experiences, and green job crafters can develop unique, eco-friendly services that lead to greater customer satisfaction and brand enhancement.

Theoretical contribution

First, it extends the limited literature linking theory on organizational culture with theory on sustainability. Building on past studies which document the impact of organizational culture on different employee behaviors (Schein, 2010), the current study demonstrates more narrowly that green organizational culture is a key antecedent of OCBE, thus stretching culture theory down into the environmental management realm. It empirically shows that the shared environmental values, norms, and beliefs institutionally embedded in an organization can directly drive employees to exhibit discretionary pro-environmental behaviors outside their formal job role requirements (Boiral, 2009).

Second, the research provides a novel contribution to theory by extending social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1986) to the sustainability domain which indicates that when there is a strong green organizational culture, employees are inclined to identify with the organization's environmental mission, making pro-environmental

behaviours part of their self-concept. This identity connection can provide a rationalization for why employees offer OCBE, by working for the environment even without direct payback (Sidorenkov et al., 2022; Norton et al., 2015).

Last, the present study contributes to the literature of OCBE by anchoring its theoretical underpinning and enlarging its antecedent model. The aim of this study is to fill this gap and to emphasize green culture as a key factor for voluntary environmental behaviour and thus, to further develop the theoretical approach of OCBE and towards further lines of sustainability-related organizational antecedents.

To our knowledge, this is the first study to demonstrate the strong influence of green organizational culture on OCBE, and thus it makes a theoretical contribution to several domains, such as the elaboration of organizational culture theory, the social identity theory, the psychological climate, and the OCBE literature. It provides a strong theoretical linkage from firm level cultural values to employee level discretionary environmental behavior, and thus improves our understanding of the process of embedding sustainability in employee behavior.

Limitations and Recommendations

This research identifies some significant limitations, despite its considerable theoretical and managerial contributions. The utilization of a cross-sectional design to investigate putative causal links among the variables constitutes the primary drawback of this study. For instance, an employee contend that desired green behavior can also be a precondition for increased well-being and the use of more effective job crafting techniques . Alternatively, employees having pro environmental behavior easily modify their jobs to sustain the desired environment. Based on theoretical justifications and previous study findings, we selected the particular sequence. However, unless they are confirmed in longitudinal investigations, the current findings remain preliminary.

The study analyzed the data quantitatively; on a close ended questionnaire, we advise future studies to apply mixed approaches to deepen our grasp of the model. To better understand the connection between green behavior and green culture, research models might be constructed in subsequent studies by first gathering qualitative data. The model may then be tested by gathering quantitative data.

Job crafting is not possible with autonomy or organizational support. Therefore, these variables may also be considered for further studies.

References

- Agyabenh-Mensah, Y., Baah, C., & Afum, E. (2024). Do the roles of green supply chain learning, green employee creativity, and green organizational citizenship behavior really matter in circular supply chain performance?. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 67(3), 609-631.
- Alola, U. V., Cop, S., & Tarkang, M. E. (2022). Green training an effective strategy for a cleaner environment: Study on hotel employees. *Journal of Public Affairs*, 22(3), e2489.

- Al-Swidi, A. K., Gelaidan, H. M., & Saleh, R. M. (2021). The joint impact of green human resource management, leadership and organizational culture on employees' green behaviour and organisational environmental performance. *Journal of cleaner production*, 316, 128112.
- Bakker, A. B., Tims, M., & Derks, D. (2012). Proactive personality and job performance: The role of job crafting and work engagement. *Human relations*, 65(10), 1359-1378.
- Blau, P. M. 1964. *Exchange and Power in Social Life*. New York: Wiley
- Boehnlein, P., & Baum, M. (2022). Does job crafting always lead to employee well-being and performance? Meta-analytical evidence on the moderating role of societal culture. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 33(4), 647-685.
- Boiral, O. (2009). Greening the corporation through organizational citizenship behaviors. *Journal of business ethics*, 87, 221-236.
- Boiral, O., & Paillé, P. (2012). Organizational citizenship behaviour for the environment: Measurement and validation. *Journal of business ethics*, 109, 431-445.
- Chandra, K., Arafah, W., & Basri, Y. Z. (2021). Analysis of the effect of green organizational culture on organizational performance and competitive advantages of green through green innovation in manufacturing industries. *Journal of Hunan University Natural Sciences*, 48(6).
- Chen, Y. S. (2011). Green organizational identity: sources and consequence. *Management decision*, 49(3), 384-404.
- Chen, Y. S., Lin, S. H., Lin, C. Y., Hung, S. T., Chang, C. W., & Huang, C. W. (2020). Improving green product development performance from green vision and organizational culture perspectives. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 27(1), 222-231.
- Darvishmotevali, M., & Altinay, L. (2022). Toward pro-environmental performance in the hospitality industry: Empirical evidence on the mediating and interaction analysis. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 31(4), 431-457.
- Deb, S. K., Das, M. K., Voumik, L. C., Nafi, S. M., Rashid, M., & Esquivias, M. A. (2023). The Environmental Effects Of Tourism: Analyzing The Impact Of Tourism. Global Trade, Consumption Expenditure, Electricity, and Pppulation on Environmental in Leading Global Tourist Destination. *GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 51, 1703-1716.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The " what " and " why " of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268.
- Demerouti, E., Bakker, A. B., & Gevers, J. M. (2015). Job crafting and extra-role behavior: The role of work engagement and flourishing. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 91, 87-96.
- Dumont, J., Shen, J., & Deng, X. (2017). Effects of green HRM practices on employee workplace green behavior: The role of psychological green climate and employee green values. *Human resource management*, 56(4), 613-627.

- Elshaer, I. A., Azazz, A. M., & Fayyad, S. (2022). Underdog environmental expectations and environmental organizational citizenship behavior in the hotel industry: Mediation of desire to prove others wrong and individual green values as a moderator. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(15), 9501.
- Faraz, N. A., Ahmed, F., Ying, M., & Mehmood, S. A. (2021). The interplay of green servant leadership, self-efficacy, and intrinsic motivation in predicting employees' pro-environmental behavior. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(4), 1171-1184.
- Galpin, T., Whittington, J. L., & Bell, G. (2015). Is your sustainability strategy sustainable? Creating a culture of sustainability. *Corporate Governance*, 15(1), 1-17.
- Garg, S., & Arora, R. G. (2025). Examining the Influence of Green Human Resource Practices on Organisational Citizenship Behaviour for Environment in Indian Banking: mediating role of green crafting through JD-R theory perspectives. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 1-41.
- Govindarajulu, N., & Daily, B. F. (2004). Motivating employees for environmental improvement. *Industrial management & data systems*, 104(4), 364-372.
- Gürlek, M., & Tuna, M. (2018). Reinforcing competitive advantage through green organizational culture and green innovation. *The service industries journal*, 38(7-8), 467-491.
- Gurmani, J. K., Khan, N. U., Khalique, M., Yasir, M., Obaid, A., & Sabri, N. A. A. (2021). Do environmental transformational leadership predicts organizational citizenship behavior towards environment in hospitality industry: using structural equation modelling approach. *Sustainability*, 13(10), 5594.
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European business review*, 31(1), 2-24.
- Hart, S. L. (1995). A natural-resource-based view of the firm. *Academy of management review*, 20(4), 986-1014.
- Hornung, S., & Rousseau, D. M. (2007). Active on the job—proactive in change: How autonomy at work contributes to employee support for organizational change. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 43(4), 401-426.
- Irfan, M., Ullah, S., Razzaq, A., Cai, J., & Adebayo, T. S. (2023). Unleashing the dynamic impact of tourism industry on energy consumption, economic output, and environmental quality in China: A way forward towards environmental sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 387, 135778.
- Jackson, S. E., Ones, D. S., & Dilchert, S. (2012). *Managing human resources for environmental sustainability* (Vol. 32). John Wiley & Sons.
- Kang, D. S., & Bartlett, K. R. (2013). The role of perceived external prestige in predicting customer-oriented citizenship behaviors. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 24(3), 285-312.
- Kenny, D.A. (2018), "Moderation", available at: <http://davidakenny.net/cm/moderation.htm>

- Khan, N. U., Saufi, R. A., & Ahmed, A. (2021). Antecedents of organizational citizenship behavior towards the environment in manufacturing organizations: using a structural equation modeling approach. *Business Process Management Journal*, 27(4), 1054-1087.
- Kim, A., Kim, Y., Han, K., Jackson, S. E., & Ployhart, R. E. (2017). Multilevel influences on voluntary workplace green behavior: Individual differences, leader behavior, and coworker advocacy. *Journal of management*, 43(5), 1335-1358.
- Kock, N. (2016). Hypothesis testing with confidence intervals and P values in PLS-SEM. *International Journal of e-Collaboration (IJeC)*, 12(3), 1-6.
- Lasrado, F., & Zakaria, N. (2020). Go green! Exploring the organizational factors that influence self-initiated green behavior in the United Arab Emirates. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 37(3), 823-850.
- Li, H., Jin, H., Hua, Y., Kong, C., & Lin, L. (2011). Green research based on cultural three-hierarchy theory. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 4(3), 196-198.
- Liao, H., Toya, K., Lepak, D. P., & Hong, Y. (2009). Do they see eye to eye? Management and employee perspectives of high-performance work systems and influence processes on service quality. *Journal of applied psychology*, 94(2), 371.
- Liu, X., & Yu, X. (2023). Green transformational leadership and employee organizational citizenship behavior for the environment in the manufacturing industry: A social information processing perspective. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 1097655.
- Luu, T. T. (2019). Green human resource practices and organizational citizenship behavior for the environment: The roles of collective green crafting and environmentally specific servant leadership. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 27(8), 1167-1196.
- Lyons, P. (2008). The crafting of jobs and individual differences. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 23(1), 25-36.
- Martínez-Martínez, A., Cegarra-Navarro, J. G., Garcia-Perez, A., & Wensley, A. (2019). Knowledge agents as drivers of environmental sustainability and business performance in the hospitality sector. *Tourism management*, 70, 381-389.
- Mughal, M. F., Cai, S., Faraz, N. A., Haiying, C., & Poulouva, P. (2024). Green servant leadership and employees' workplace green behavior: interplay of green self-efficacy, green work engagement, and environmental passion. *Current Psychology*, 43(33), 26806-26822.
- Muisyo, P. K., Qin, S., Ho, T. H., Julius, M. M., & Barisoava Andriamandresy, T. (2022). Implications of GHRM on organisational citizenship behaviour: the mediating role of enablers of green culture. *International Journal of Manpower*, 43(3), 719-741.
- Niessen, C., Weseler, D., & Kostova, P. (2016). When and why do individuals craft their jobs? The role of individual motivation and work characteristics for job crafting. *Human relations*, 69(6), 1287-1313.

- Norton, T. A., Zacher, H., & Ashkanasy, N. M. (2015). Pro-environmental organizational culture and climate. *The psychology of green organizations*, 322-348.
- Öğretmenoğlu, M., Akova, O., & Göktepe, S. (2022). The mediating effects of green organizational citizenship on the relationship between green transformational leadership and green creativity: evidence from hotels. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 5(4), 734-751.
- Paillé, P., Boiral, O., & Chen, Y. (2013). Linking environmental management practices and organizational citizenship behaviour for the environment: a social exchange perspective. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(18), 3552-3575.
- Paillé, P., Chen, Y., Boiral, O., & Jin, J. (2014). The impact of human resource management on environmental performance: An employee-level study. *Journal of Business ethics*, 121, 451-466.
- Paillé, P., Mejía-Morelos, J. H., Marché-Paillé, A., Chen, C. C., & Chen, Y. (2016). Corporate greening, exchange process among co-workers, and ethics of care: An empirical study on the determinants of pro-environmental behaviors at coworkers-level. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 136(3), 655-673.
- Petrou, P., Demerouti, E., Peeters, M. C., Schaufeli, W. B., & Hetland, J. (2012). Crafting a job on a daily basis: Contextual correlates and the link to work engagement. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 33(8), 1120-1141.
- Pham, N. T., Tučková, Z., & Jabbour, C. J. C. (2019). Greening the hospitality industry: How do green human resource management practices influence organizational citizenship behavior in hotels? A mixed-methods study. *Tourism management*, 72, 386-399.
- Pham, T. N., Phan, Q. P. T., Tučková, Z., Vo, T. N., & Nguyen, L. H. (2018). Enhancing the organizational citizenship behavior for the environment: the roles of green training and organizational culture. *Management & Marketing-Challenges for the Knowledge Society*. 13(4), 1174-1189.
- Qu, X., Khan, A., Yahya, S., Zafar, A. U., & Shahzad, M. (2022). Green core competencies to prompt green absorptive capacity and bolster green innovation: the moderating role of organization's green culture. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 65(3), 536-561.
- Robertson, J. L., & Barling, J. (2013). Greening organizations through leaders' influence on employees' pro-environmental behaviors. *Journal of organizational behavior*, 34(2), 176-194.
- Roscoe, S., Subramanian, N., Jabbour, C. J., & Chong, T. (2019). Green human resource management and the enablers of green organisational culture: Enhancing a firm's environmental performance for sustainable development. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 28(5), 737-749.
- Saeed, B. B., Afsar, B., Hafeez, S., Khan, I., Tahir, M., & Afridi, M. A. (2019). Promoting employee's proenvironmental behavior through green human resource management practices. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 26(2), 424-438.

- Sarstedt, M., Hair Jr, J. F., & Ringle, C. M. (2023). "PLS-SEM: indeed a silver bullet"—retrospective observations and recent advances. *Journal of Marketing theory and Practice*, 31(3), 261-275.
- Schein, E. H. (2010). *Organizational culture and leadership* (4th ed.). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Sidorenkov, A. V., Borokhovski, E. F., & Vorontsov, D. V. (2023). Associations of employees' identification and citizenship behavior in organization: A systematic review and a meta-analysis. *Management Review Quarterly*, 73(2), 695-729.
- Song, M., Yang, M. X., Zeng, K. J., & Feng, W. (2020). Green knowledge sharing, stakeholder pressure, absorptive capacity, and green innovation: Evidence from Chinese manufacturing firms. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(3), 1517-1531.
- Srivastava, S., Pathak, D., Soni, S., & Dixit, A. (2024). Does green transformational leadership reinforce green creativity? The mediating roles of green organizational culture and green mindfulness. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 37(3), 619-640.
- Subramanian, N., & Suresh, M. (2023). Green organizational culture in manufacturing SMEs: an analysis of causal relationships. *International Journal of Manpower*, 44(5), 789-809.
- Susanto, S., Kosasih, H., Julitawaty, W., Syaifullah, S., & Pebri, P. (2025). Organizational Trust and Readiness for Change: Its Impact on Employee Performance Through Job Crafting (Empirical Study at PT Saudara Buana Samudera Medan). *Society*, 13(1), 35-57.
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (2004). The social identity theory of intergroup behavior. In *Political psychology* (pp. 276-293). Psychology Press.
- Temminck, E., Mearns, K., & Fruhen, L. (2015). Motivating employees towards sustainable behaviour. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 24(6), 402-412.
- Tims, M., & Bakker, A. B. (2010). Job crafting: Towards a new model of individual job redesign. *South Africa Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 36(2), 1-9.
- Tims, M., Bakker, A. B., & Derks, D. (2012). Development and validation of the job crafting scale. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 80(1), 173-186.
- Tims, M., Bakker, A. B., & Derks, D. (2013). The impact of job crafting on job demands, job resources, and well-being. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 18(2), 230.
- Vogel, R. M., Rodell, J. B., & Lynch, J. W. (2016). Engaged and productive misfits: How job crafting and leisure activity mitigate the negative effects of value incongruence. *Academy of Management Journal*, 59(5), 1561-1584.
- Wrzesniewski, A., & Dutton, J. E. (2001). Crafting a job: Revisioning employees as active crafters of their work. *Academy of management review*, 26(2), 179-201.
- Wrzesniewski, A., LoBuglio, N., Dutton, J. E., & Berg, J. M. (2013). Job crafting and cultivating positive meaning and identity in work. In *Advances in positive organizational psychology* (Vol. 1, pp. 281-302). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.

- Yang, Y., Jiang, L., & Wang, Y. (2023). Why do hotels go green? Understanding TripAdvisor GreenLeaders participation. *International journal of contemporary hospitality management*, 35(5), 1670-1690.
- Yeşiltaş, M., Gürlek, M., & Kenar, G. (2022). Organizational green culture and green employee behavior: Differences between green and non-green hotels. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 343, 131051.
- Zaidi, H., & Azmi, F. T. (2024). Workplace pro-environmental behaviour: A review and bibliometric analysis. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 73(1), 158-185.
- Zhang, F., & Parker, S. K. (2019). Reorienting job crafting research: A hierarchical structure of job crafting concepts and integrative review. *Journal of organizational behavior*, 40(2), 126-146.
- Zientara, P., & Zamojska, A. (2018). Green organizational climates and employee pro-environmental behaviour in the hotel industry. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 26(7), 1142-1159.